

EXPLORING THE IMPACT OF COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY ON THE ACADEMIC SUCCESS OF BSIT STUDENTS

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Exploring the Impact of Computer Technology on the Academic Success of BSIT Students

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Abstract

This study determined the impact of computer technology on the academic achievement of students. The study was conducted at Cebu Technological University- Tuburan Campus. The respondents of this study were students taking up a Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology Major in Computer Technology. The researchers made a questionnaire was used to gather data from the said respondents. The research utilized qualitative methods with the utilization of statistical tools, percentage, weighted mean, and ranking. On the personal background of the respondents are willing and determined to finish their studies before getting married. The findings on the monthly allowance of the students, it was found out (69) 85% of the students have an allowance of 1,000- 2,000 per month. It was revealed that in using computer technology the students' most common use was the Educational purpose. It was the reason for using computer technology. One of the Problems that students met was "Lack of study habits" which means they don't have enough time to study their lessons and that can affect their academic achievements. It was concluded that the computer is the most needed for technology students. Based on the result of the study the researchers recommend implementing seminars and training to the students for the awareness in using computer technology and more computer laboratory for the students.

Keywords: *Computer technology, academic achievement, Bachelor of Science in Industrial Technology (BSIT), qualitative method, lack of the study habits*

Introduction

Improving technology has brought great easiness together in every field from military to industry, from health to education. Especially the development and prevalence of Computer Technology and usability for multipurpose aims to provide not only speed and economy but also visual and sound opportunities. Computer Technology, which started abacus and now has come to core duo processors, will be a great need even at home from now on (Demici, 2006).

These technological developments and technological products being brought with them forced Traditional Education (TI) systems to be changed and add new ones to the means and tools used (Anonim, 1997). It is possible to follow and keep up with the times if only raising the effect of the educational system. Because our time is technology time, it is needed to add technological opportunities into it and use technology. Educational materials as assistant materials are among the tools to make instruction more beneficial, lasting, and pleasurable. Computers and instructional materials being used as both tools and methods are effective for students in increasing their concentration on the course, understanding the lesson, and synthesizing and improving positive thoughts for the course. Instructional Materials make the topic clearer and more lasting by making the abstract topics concrete (Cepni et al., 2004; Demirel, 2004).

Today's students are growing with visual tools like television, video, computers, and the internet. It is not possible to get these students' interest in the TI method used in the past. Technological developments have resulted in a big gap between the ways of teaching methods at school and getting information in society in the last quarter of the 20th century. Because most of the students get the information via visual content sources like computers and televisions, which are used in daily life very much, it is made difficult to teach something to the students by traditional methods (Cepni et al., 2004; London, 2005).

According to Anyanwu (2003), they have faced two main difficulties. On one hand, student academic achievement is hard to observe and there is still confusion about its definition. On the other hand, the computer is evolving technologies and their effects are difficult to isolate from their environment.

There is no standard definition for student achievement. The standard approach focuses on achievement and curricula how students understand the subjects and obtain their certificate or their marks. However, a more extensive definition deals with competencies, skills, and attitudes learned through education experience (Kamba, 2009).

The effect of computer usage on learning is currently about the internet to facilitate teaching and learning. Computers are the technologies used in conveying, manipulating, and storage of data by electronic means, they provide an array of powerful tools that may help in transforming the present isolated teacher-centered and text-bound classrooms into rich, student-focused, interactive knowledge environments (Ongunsola, 2005). The relationship between the use of computers and student achievement is not clear, and there are contradictory results in the literature. Earlier economic research has failed to provide a clear consensus concerning the effect on students' achievement (Kamba, 2009).

The direct link between computer use and students' achievement has been the focus of extensive literature during the last two decades. Several studies have tried to explain the role and the added value of computer technologies in classrooms and on students' achievement. The first body of literature explored the impact of computer use. Since the internet revolution, there has been a shift in the literature

that focuses more on the impact of online activities; use of the internet, use of educative online platforms, digital devices, use of blogs, and wikis, etc. Looking at the link between computer usage and student achievement seems nowadays a misunderstanding of the role and nature of these technologies. In fact, since the computer is general-purpose technology (GPT), it needs to be the local context and constraints (Antonelli, 2003, Youssef, 2008)

The purpose of these study is to form and raise certain awareness to the students regarding the effects of computer technology. This study focuses only on how students taking up a Bachelor of Science and Industrial Technology major in Computer Technology perform academically with persistent use of computers.

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive method. It is an investigative process that utilizes the questionnaire was gather data and interpret the findings. A research-structured questionnaire was used as the main data-gathering tool.

Respondents

Eighty-one (81) Bachelor of Industrial Technology Major in Computer Technology students in Cebu Technological University Tuburan Campus participated in the study. Table 1 presents the age and gender of the respondent, marital status, and their monthly allowance.

Table 1. *Frequencies and Percentages According to the Variables of the Study*

	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	39	48
	Female	42	52
Age	27 and above	0	0
	24-26	4	5
	21-23	23	28
	18-20	54	67
Marital Status	Single	78	96
	Married	3	4
Monthly Allowance	Php 5000-6000	3	4
	Php 3000-4000	9	11
	Php 1000-2000	69	85

Procedure

The data were gathered through a test and survey questionnaire. The researchers surveyed all BSIT student respondents in the Tuburan Campus. The questionnaire was distributed evenly to researchers first to have equal participation and the researchers distributed the questionnaire to the respondents. The researchers chose random respondents per student. Most questionnaires were collected right after respondents answered and some were collected the day after the distribution on the respondent’s vacant time. The researchers made it to the point that the respondents will answer the questionnaire honestly and sincerely.

Data Analysis

Weighted Mean was used to determine the profile of the respondents as to age and gender, marital status, monthly allowance, and academic achievements of the students. To determine the extent of the respondents in the purpose of using computer technology, a five-point Likert scale was adapted with 1 as very low to 5 as very high with means interpreted as (1.00 – 1.8 = Never, 1.8 – 2.6 = Seldom, 2.61 – 3.4 = Sometimes, 3.41 – 4.2 = Often, 4.21 – 5.0 = Always).

Results and Discussion

Table 2. *Means of Learners’ Perception of the Use or Purpose of the Computer Technology*

Purpose	5	4	3	2	1	TWP	WM	I
Gaming	38	30	10	3	0	346	4.27	A
Educational	60	21	0	0	0	384	4.7	A
Communication	40	30	11	0	0	353	3.36	S

Legend: 4.21–5.00 Always; 3.41–4.20 Often; 2.61–3.40 Sometimes; 1.81–2.60 Seldom; 1.00–1.80 Never

Table 2 pertains to the ranking of items on the purposes of computer technology to BSIT students. As shown in Table 2, for the students first rank of the purpose is “Educational Purpose” the second rank is “Communication”, third and last rank is “Gamming and leisure time/ spare time. It shows that Educational purposes are the most common reason for using computer technology. The result implies that computer technology is very useful to the life of students they can use it for educational purposes that can help them get a higher

academic achievement.

Table 3. *Hours of Exposure to Computer*

<i>Hours of exposure to computer</i>	<i>Students</i>	<i>Rank</i>
5-6 hours	14	3
3-4 hours	27	2
1-2 hours	58	1

Table 3 pertains the ranking of hours being exposed to computer technology for daily basis by the respondents. As shown in Table 3, the respondents' first rank in exposure is 1-2 hours, second is 3-4 hours, and third is 5-6 hours. It reveals that the respondents are exposed to computer technology for as long as 1-2 hours per day and it takes away if needed. It implies that students have a time limitation in using computer technology which can affect their academic achievement.

Table 4. *Problems Met with the Use of Computer Technology*

<i>Problems Met</i>	<i>Students</i>	<i>Rank</i>
Lack of Study habits	41	1
No time to make projects	31	4
My grades are affected because my allowance for projects and output is consumed.	36	2
I have a low grades because I am addicted to games and I don't have an interest in studying.	35	3
I began to have health problems further leading to my absences in my class and affecting my study.	29	5

Table 4 pertains to the ranking of problems met by the respondents in dealing with computer technology. As shown in Table 4, the respondent's first rank is; Lack of study habits; second in rank is, My grades are affected because my allowance for projects and outputs are consumed; third in rank is, I have low grades because I am addicted to games and I don't have interest for study; fourth in rank is, No time in making projects; Fifth in rank is, I begin to have health problems further lead to my absences in my class and affect my study. It shows that the most common problem met by the respondents in utilizing computer technology is a Lack of study habits that can affect their academic achievements. It implies that students being exposed to computer technology don't have enough time for their study which can affect their academic achievements because instead of studying they are attached to computer technology playing games or being attached to social media.

Table 5. *Level of the Academic Achievement of the Students in Computer Systems Hardware Subject*

<i>Interpretation</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Superior	22	27.16
Very Good	53	65.43
Good	6	7.40
Fair	0	0
Poor	0	0
Total	81	100

Legend: 1.0 Excellent; 1.1-1.5 Superior; 1.6-2.0 Very Good; 2.1-2.5 Good; 2.6-3.0 Fair or Passing; 3.1-4.0 Conditional; 4.1-5.0 Failures; NG No Grade

As reflected in Table 5, showed the grades of the students and the purpose of using computer technology and it reveals that computer technology did not affect the academic achievements of the students. All of them have passed their major. The result implies that computer technology is helpful to students for educational purposes they can search for the information they need and with the help of computer technology they can make their output beautiful and presentable. Therefore, computer technology helps students to achieve higher levels of academic achievement.

Conclusions

Based on the data revealed computer technology is very useful to the life of students in way of educational purposes, they can easily search for pieces of information they need. But also computer technology is useful to students in communication. Based on the data revealed in the research the highest rank is the educational purposes which is a good result because students are using computer technology for a good purpose, but some are using computer technology for gaming which is not good for the students. Therefore, the higher students' grades in their major computer technology (computer system hardware), the more likely they will be responsible enough to use computer technology knowing the good and the bad effects of it on their academic achievements.

The University may want to propose and put into reality a computer laboratory availability that offers proportionate numbers of computers to the number of students expected in a school year. The university may need an internet connection available in all areas of the university. With this, students who have small phones, tab, or laptops need not use the computer laboratory instead just get connected and will be a smooth and harmonious population within the university in the aspect of using computer technology. The University may need to conduct seminars and programs within the school year among the students in different courses especially computer major students which will offer great understanding and wisdom to the proper usage of computer technology. And also discuss the positive and negative effects of computer technology that may affect their academic achievements.

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